

The Influence Of Organizational Culture, Financial Compensation And Interactional Organizational Justice On Normative Commitment And Employee Performance Of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember

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Abstract- The role of human resources is inseparable for Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember in its success in implementing the Drinking Water Supply System (SPAM) in Jember Regency. One of the efforts made by the Directors of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember in encouraging increased employee performance is by establishing organizational culture, financial compensation and interactional organizational justice towards normative commitment and employee performance at Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember which can be used as a guide for all members of the organization in implementing every job. The results of this research show that organizational culture does not have a significant effect on normative commitment but does have a significant effect on employee performance. Financial compensation and interactional organizational justice have a significant effect on normative commitment but do not have a significant effect on employee performance. Normative commitment has a significant effect on employee performance. Normative commitment does not have a significant effect in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. Normative commitment has a significant effect in mediating the effect of financial compensation on employee performance. Normative commitment has a significant effect in mediating the influence of interactional organizational justice on employee performance.

Keywords: Organizational culture, financial compensation, interactional organizational justice, normative commitment and employee performance.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important aspect in an organization. No matter how sophisticated the facilities and infrastructure an organization is, it will be meaningless if it is not supported by the expertise of human resources within the organization. Therefore, human resources must be managed professionally in order to contribute to achieving organizational goals. According to Wulandari (2020: 191), the aim of managing human resources professionally is to create a balance between employee needs and organizational demands in order to develop productively.

The challenges in managing human resources today are very complicated, on the one hand organizations are always faced with an uncertain business situation, many changes in the business environment and increasingly tight business competition make organizations inevitably have to move dynamically in order to survive in facing every challenge. he faced. According to Bukit (2017:15). The challenges and difficulties faced by organizations must be managed effectively and efficiently. Taking into account the large diversity of human resources today, human resource management must be able to create effective communication, increase employee competence by providing training, create a comfortable work environment and be able to provide feedback based on the performance achievements of each employee.

In implementing regional autonomy, the Regional Government obtains broad authority in increasing Regional Original Income (PAD). One of the efforts made by regional governments to increase PAD revenues is by forming Regional Owned Enterprises (BUMD). Of course, the existence of BUMD in a region is expected to contribute to regional development and assist the Regional Government in improving the welfare of the people of that region. According to Nasir (2019:35), BUMD covers various fields, including: the agricultural trade business sector, the service/trade sector, the mineral resource management sector, the banking sector, the insurance sector and so on.

Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember, formerly known as PDAM Jember, is one of the Jember Regency Regional-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) which operates in the drinking water services sector (Jember Regency Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2022). As a company owned by the regional government, Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember is expected to be able to contribute to regional development through the profits it generates. Apart from being profit oriented, Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember is also expected to provide good service to the community in providing clean water (public service oriented). In carrying out its duties as a profit-oriented company, Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember must increase revenue through water sales as well as increase customer growth and be able to reduce the level of water loss every year.

Table 1. Target Revenue, Addition of Customers and Water Loss Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember 2019-2021

Year	Income (Rp)	Additional customers (SR)	Lost water (%)
2019	39,057,912,000	4,070	21,98

2020	50,175,994,000	6,661	21,65
2021	57,288,425,000	9,033	23,49

Source: Perumdam Work Plan and Budget for 2019-2021.

Achieving the set target is not an easy thing, it requires the contribution of all employees to achieve the set target. Likewise, in carrying out its duties as a public service oriented company, Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember feels the need to carry out continuous performance improvements (continuous improvement). This can be seen from the ratings and reviews given by several customers on Google Reviews. where Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember only received 2 out of 5 stars.

The role of human resources is inseparable for Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember in its success in implementing the Drinking Water Supply System (SPAM) in Jember Regency. Considering that the human resources aspect is one of the most important aspects in the Drinking Water Supply System (National Urban Water Supply Project, 2020). This proves that managing the provision of quality clean water services requires qualified human resources. Therefore, the Directors of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember as top managers in the organization always encourage all employees of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember to continue to improve their performance productivity, so that Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember can achieve the targets that have been set and be able to carry out their duties as a public service oriented company better. Again.

Productivity is closely related to human resources, which is what makes company leaders pay attention to the performance aspects of each employee. With high productivity, the profits obtained by the organization will also increase. Employee performance achievements are often referred to as performance or job performance. Employees can be said to have good performance if they successfully complete each job they are responsible for based on a mutually agreed quality and quantity perspective (Silaen et al., 2021:2). Employee performance that is managed appropriately can contribute to achieving the goals and targets set by the company. So managing and managing employee performance must be carried out continuously and involve the role of all human resources in the organization.

Increasing employee performance is closely related to how to build commitment to employees. Employees who have high organizational commitment always try hard and are responsible in fighting for the company's progress, and employees do not hesitate to make a greater contribution than what the company expects. Organizational commitment is a manifestation of employee alignment with their organization and a situation where employees still want to be in the organization to help the company achieve its goals (Badrudin, 2019:20). Companies basically want every employee to have high organizational commitment. Employees who are committed to the organization will always improve their performance, both individual, group and organizational performance in a better direction and will voluntarily make maximum contributions for the progress of their organization (Maryani, 2018: 73). On the other hand, low employee organizational commitment can potentially reduce their performance. According to Wahyudi and Salam (2020:4), employees who are committed to their organization are a luxury for their organization. This is because it is not easy to foster commitment in employees, remembering that commitment is a good thing and that good will return to those who do it. Commitment is also formed through a long series of processes and becomes stronger along with the experiences each member of the organization goes through.

Organizational commitment itself is divided into three dimensions, namely affective commitment, continuous commitment and normative commitment (Ariyani et al., 2020: 113). Each member of the organization certainly has a different level of commitment from one another. Organization members who have affective commitment have a much stronger desire to be involved in every job so that the organization can achieve its stated goals, on the other hand, organizational members who choose to stay in the organization because their efforts are not optimal (Widiana, 2015: 34). Meanwhile, employees who have normative commitment always have the perception that they are obliged to give back for everything the organization gives them (Aprilia et.al., 2022). Research results from Sambung (2016) resulted in the finding that of the three dimensions of organizational commitment, normative commitment is the highest factor in influencing employee work behavior in the public service sector. The research results of Sambung (2016) are in line with research conducted by Ariyani et al., (2020), where normative commitment has an influence on the performance of BUMD employees in Semarang City. The higher the normative commitment an employee has, the higher the employee's productivity. Employees with normative commitment feel obliged to give their best performance as a form of obligation to what the organization gives them. Organization members who have normative commitments also always remain part of the organization because they feel that they have benefited from being in the organization.

One of the efforts made by the Directors of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember to encourage increased employee performance is by establishing a competitive organizational culture and an organizational culture that can be used as a guide for all members of the organization in carrying out their work. The organizational culture continues to be managed and becomes a management tool in influencing the behavior of each member of the organization to produce increased work ethic and organizational productivity. According to Hadju and Adam (2019: 127), organizational culture can be used as a foundation in maintaining an organization's competitive advantage. Mahardani and Paramadina (2019:134) further explained that organizational culture can be used as a tool to address the dynamics of the internal and external environment, along with all the problems that exist in the organization so that organizational culture can be used as a bridge for the organization to achieve its goals.

Apart from forming a strong organizational culture, a common method often used by organizations to improve employee performance is by providing compensation (Gadung and Suwanto, 2020:237). Providing compensation to employees consists of financial compensation and non-financial compensation, where financial compensation includes payments to employees in the form of salaries, bonuses and commissions. Meanwhile, non-financial compensation is something that employees receive in forms other than money (Candra, 2018:2). Providing financial compensation at Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember does not only include salary but also in the form of bonuses and educational allowances and religious allowances which are given annually. Of course, providing compensation in financial form that employees receive can foster the commitment of all employees to continue to provide their best performance as a form of normative responsibility for what the company has provided. The purpose of providing

compensation is as a form of company appreciation for employees, ensuring fairness and retaining employees. Fair compensation can stimulate employees to carry out their work better and be more responsible (Mujanah, 2019:6). Compensation to employees must also be balanced by considering employee contributions and employee needs. Providing excessive compensation cannot be justified because it can harm the company and its employees. According to (Hernita, 2015:3) providing excessive compensation can reduce the company's competitiveness.

Another effort made by Perum's Directors to achieve the set goals is to implement accountable management. One activity that cannot be separated from management activities is the organizing process. The organizing process is reflected through the organizational structure, division of work as well as the relationship pattern between superiors and subordinates. According to Kristanto (2015: 88), organizational justice for employees does not only include aspects of financial compensation, but also the relationship between superiors and subordinates. Organizational justice can be measured from 3 things: namely salary fairness in accordance with the work carried out by employees, organizational fairness in terms of providing opportunities for each member to participate in decision making and fairness of relationships between superiors and subordinates that exist in the organizational process. Organizational justice related to the combination of trust between subordinates and superiors is referred to as interactional organizational justice (Aufan, 2021:331). Interactional organizational justice includes justice where employees in the organization are treated with respect, dignity and when making decisions superiors care about employee rights and in implementing decisions made, leaders always convey information, instructions clearly and logically (Muttaqien and Sulisityan, 2021: 118).

Several studies have been conducted that focus on improving performance through organizational culture, compensation and organizational justice, but there are still several differences in the research results obtained. Among them is research conducted by Badrudin (2019:80) and Kencana (2019:42), which states that organizational culture has a significant effect on employee performance as well as research conducted by Ulum et al., (2018) where good organizational culture is proven to be able to improve the performance of PDAM Lumajang employees. However, this is different from research conducted by Saputri and Muhsin (2018: 1146) which states that organizational culture has no direct effect on performance. This research is in line with research conducted by Cobbinah et al. (2020:294) which states that organizational culture does not directly influence performance. Organizational culture has an influence on performance when mediated by organizational commitment. Cobbinah et al.'s research (2020), also has differences with research conducted by Budiono (2016), which states that organizational commitment cannot mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance.

Research examining the three dimensions of organizational commitment has been conducted by several researchers, including Muhyi (2021:53), who states that affective commitment has a significant effect on performance, continuous commitment has a significant effect on performance, and normative commitment has a significant effect on performance. , and simultaneously these three dimensions of organizational commitment have a significant effect on employee performance. Likewise with research by Utari and Subijanto (2020:76), which states that the three dimensions of commitment have a significant effect, both partially and simultaneously, on employee performance. So far there has been no research that specifically tests one of the three dimensions of organizational commitment. Although there are several studies that examine the effect of organizational support on performance through affective commitment as a mediating variable, so far there has been no research that examines the role of normative organizational commitment as a mediating variable between organizational support, either in the form of organizational culture, financial compensation or interactional organizational justice. performance, so it becomes an important gap that is interesting to research. It is hoped that this research can enrich scientific insight into the practical aspects of human resource management which is one of the important aspects in the drinking water supply system (SPAM) and can also be used as material for consideration in decision making in human resource management at Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember.

Based on the above phenomena, researchers are interested in conducting research on the influence of organizational culture, financial compensation and interactional organizational justice on normative commitment and employee performance at Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

A strong organizational culture is a very useful tool for directing the behavior of each member of the organization. Organizational culture can also bind motivation and act as an organizational solution if there is ambiguity. According to Taula (2020: 4), organizational culture is a pattern of basic assumptions that are closely related to beliefs, values and behavior created and developed by an organization as a basis for determining organizational direction and goals, consensus, excellence, achievement, innovation, unity. , closeness and organizational integrity, which can be used as a guideline for every member of the organization to have the same behavior in solving every internal and external problem of the organization, with a superior organizational culture, every member of the organization can support the growth and development of the organization (Badrudin, 2019: 13). The organizational culture indicators in Badrudin's research (2019:41) are as follows:

1. Innovation and Risk Taking

Measures the extent of innovation and risk taking of an employee in the organization.

2. Attention to Detail

Measures the extent of analysis, thoroughness, thoroughness and attention to detail of an employee's work in the organization.

3. Results Oriented

Measuring management's focus on making decisions that are more focused on results rather than focusing on techniques and processes in achieving these results.

4. Individual Orientation

Measuring the extent to which the organization's work activities are carried out based on the individual abilities of the organization's members.

5. Team Orientation

Measuring the extent to which the organization's work activities are carried out in work teams, not individuals.

6. Aggressiveness

Measures the extent of an employee's proactive and competitive attitude in the organization.

7. Stability

Measures the extent to which an organization's activities emphasize maintaining the status quo as opposed to growth, change or innovation.

FINANCIAL COMPENSATION

Compensation is a form of remuneration or appreciation given to members of an organization for carrying out and completing work or tasks given by the company to that individual. Compensation can be in the form of financial (money) or rewards. Such as awards, positions, working conditions and so on. A good compensation system is compensation that can guarantee satisfaction to all members of the organization (Mujanah, 2019:3). Compensation is influenced by career level and compensation can influence employee motivation and satisfaction at work. According to Tanjung (2020: 169), the aim of providing compensation to employees is to grow the company's competitive advantage through company recruitment, apart from that, human resources who have become part of the organization will always be committed to remaining part of its members. This also has an effect on the low level of employees leave the organization.

According to Mujanah (2019:4), in practice giving and determining the amount of compensation has several objectives, including:

1. Obtain quality human resources

Good compensation, attractive to applicants. So the potential for obtaining quality human resources will be greater.

2. Retain Employees

One of the causes of high turnover is uncompetitive compensation so that employees will leave the organization to look for a company that offers better compensation.

3. Guarantee Justice

With compensation management, organizations can achieve internal and external justice.

4. Respect for Employee Behavior

By providing good compensation, organizations can regulate organizational members so that they can act and behave according to the wishes of the organization, both now and in the future.

5. Controlling Costs

A rational compensation system also helps companies acquire and retain employees at a reasonable cost. Without effective compensation management, employees may be paid below or above standard.

6. Follow Government Regulations

Providing correct compensation is compensation that refers to government regulations, where the government has set a Minimum Working Wage (UMK), even though the UMK determination between regions is not the same, the provision of compensation according to the regional UMK must be applied by all companies in Indonesia.

7. Open and Transparent

Good compensation is compensation that is open, so that all members of the organization understand what components they will receive. Transparent compensation can motivate employees to improve their performance.

8. Increase Administrative Efficiency

An effective and efficient compensation system must be managed effectively and efficiently so that it is systematically integrated between one part and another.

The financial compensation indicators used in Arhas et al.'s research. (2022:139) covers:

1. Basic Salary, which is an indicator used to measure the suitability of the salary provided by the company when compared to the workload and responsibilities.
2. Incentives, indicators used to measure the provision of additional salaries beyond the basic salary, measure the appreciation given by the organization in financial form to employee work performance. These achievements can be in the form of achieving sales targets, achieving productivity levels, achieving profit targets.
3. Bonus, an indicator used to measure direct giving as compensation for high work performance for a certain period of time. Bonuses may not be given if the organization does not achieve good work results during a predetermined period of time, for example annually.
4. Benefits, an indicator used to measure the guarantees provided by the organization during retirement or health insurance.

INTERACTIONAL ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE

Organizational justice is social norms and rules that determine decision procedures for the distribution of human resources within an organization. Organizational justice regulates the provision of rewards, punishments and also the implementation of relations between employees (Munir, 2023). Organizational justice is employees' perception of the treatment they receive regarding what they provide to the organization. The organization itself is basically a system of social life, so the system must be formed based on justice, so that the system always supports the progress of the organization (Orishede, 2022:388).

Organizational justice is an employee's perception of overall justice in an organization. The more employees recognize organizational justice in treating employees, the higher their motivation, attitudes and behavior in the organization (Kaswan, 2015: 254). Organizational justice is a decision made by an organization to organizational members that reflects equality of justice in its work environment. If employees feel justice in their workplace, the enthusiasm to work well will always be embedded, and the

resulting performance will increase (Mon and Jennifer, 2022: 115). Based on research conducted by Aufan (2021:331), the indicators used in the variables of distributive organizational justice and interactional organizational justice are as follows:

1. Distributive justice
 - a) Equity, providing rewards to employees based on the contributions made by the company by employees
 - b) Equality, providing equal compensation among employees
 - c) Need, providing benefits based on employee needs
2. Interactional justice
 - a) Interpersonal justice, treating employees humanely
 - b) Informational justice, sharing relevant information between superiors and subordinates.

NORMATIVE COMMITMENT

Organizational commitment is the loyalty that employees have in their place of work, an employee's loyal attitude is shown by remaining with members of the organization and having no intention of leaving the organization under any circumstances and for any reason, and voluntarily participating in helping the organization in achieving its goals (Yusuf and Syarif, 2017:27). The opinions of experts regarding the definition or meaning of organizational commitment are as follows:

- 1) Organizational commitment is a situation where employees always side with the organization's goals, maintain their membership status, are loyal and willing to continue working well under any circumstances (Lubis and Jaya, 2019: 9)
- 2) Organizational commitment is an employee's psychological interest in the organization, which is described by being loyal, taking sides and being involved in every organizational activity (Widiana, 2015:31).
- 3) Organizational commitment is an individual's attachment to their organization to remain loyal to being part of the organization, have pride in their organization, provide effort to the organization and be able to accept the values and goals of the organization (Badrudin, 2019:20).

Based on the definition of organizational commitment, it can be concluded that the definition of organizational commitment is an employee's belief in continuing to be part of the organization under any circumstances, continuing to provide good performance to support all organizational goals and accepting all the values and norms that apply within the organization.

Indicators of organizational commitment that have been used in previous research are as follows:

1. Tjendana (2022:75), states that indicators of organizational commitment include:
 - a) Strong desire to remain part of the organization
 - b) The desire to fulfill the organization's desires
 - c) Awareness in accepting the values and goals of the organization.
2. According to Darmawan (2013: 169), there are 3 (three) types of indicators of organizational commitment, namely:
 - a) Affective Commitment is organizational commitment which measures emotional attraction to beliefs in organizational values. Where affective commitment includes 3 elements, namely: a strong desire to have a career in the organization, a sense of trust in the organization, devotion to the organization
 - b) Sustainability Commitment, continuance commitment is a commitment that members of an organization have towards their organization based on elements of profit and loss, not based on awareness, where members who have a continuance commitment believe in the potential losses experienced if members of the organization leave their organization. The elements of organizational commitment include: Employees' love for the organization, desire to stay with their job, willingness to put the interests of the organization before their personal interests.
 - c) Normative Commitment, Commitment that organizational members have for moral and ethical reasons. Where normative commitment has 3 elements, namely: loyalty to the organization, happiness at work, pride in working for the organization.

According to Wardhana (2021:204) explains that the essence of normative commitment is the obligation to remain part of the organization (ought to stay with the organization). Normative commitment is a moral obligation felt by employees not to move to another organization. The indicators of normative commitment are:

- 1) The individual employee's need to remain in the organization.
- 2) There is responsibility to remain in the organization.
- 3) Consideration of leaving the organization results in self-sacrifice or regret
- 4) There is a feeling of risk (risky) about leaving the organization
- 5) There are negative consequences if you leave the organization.
- 6) The employee's individual belief in accepting the values, norms, rules and goals of the organization.

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

In the large Indonesian dictionary, performance means activities that produce something. Several researchers have opinions regarding the definition of performance, including:

1. Asnawi (2019:11), states that performance is an activity carried out for the purpose of achieving targets determined by the organization in a certain period. Employee performance is also an activity that involves evaluation from management, performance is a two-way relationship between the organization and its members, the organization wants its members to improve their performance in order to provide benefits to the organization and on the other hand members also try to improve their performance to obtain rewards in the form of promotions and development. himself.
2. Performance is the level of achievement of an activity in order to achieve the organization's goals, vision and mission legally and not against the law. Regarding performance in order to realize the organization's vision and mission, it must be formulated through strategy or planning. Performance includes individual performance and group performance. Where individual performance is closely related to the employee's competence, skills, attitudes, behavior and insight. Meanwhile, organizational

performance includes flexibility, adaptability, conflict resolution and relationships with other agencies or organizations (Budianto and Mochklas, 2020:11).

3. Performance is an attitude or action, not a noun. Performance is an action consisting of several elements, performance is also a continuous process so it can be said that performance does not refer to momentary achievements. In organizations, performance is often associated with managing human resources in order to achieve desired results. Organizational performance also includes the company's productivity and the productivity of its human resources (Huseno, 2016: 88).

From several expert opinions, researchers can conclude that the definition of employee performance is an employee's ongoing activities towards the targets, vision and mission that have been set by the company. Every employee must improve their performance because increasing performance is related to increasing company productivity which can have an impact on the profits generated. According to Badruddin (2019), employee performance indicators used in employee performance research are as follows:

1) Working quantity

It is an indicator that measures the standard of an employee's work from the comparison of output to targets assigned to employees in a specified period.

2) Quality of work

Work quality is an indicator of employee performance which is seen from the quality of work that has been completed based on standards or demands from the organization.

3) Punctuality

Each job has certain characteristics, some job characteristics are interdependent with other jobs, so punctuality in this case is important so that other jobs can be completed quickly or are not neglected.

4) Presence

Attendance is an indicator of employee performance, therefore attendance indicators can measure how responsible an employee is.

5) Collaboration ability

Performance does not only cover one individual in the organization, because there are several types of work that must be completed as a group, therefore communication and collaboration skills between one individual and another are very important. Collaboration ability is an indicator used to describe employee performance in working together, providing important input to superiors and respecting fellow members.

RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on a literature review or previous research that has been conducted regarding organizational culture, work engagement, compensation, organizational commitment and performance, the conceptual framework that the author has successfully developed is as follows:

Figure 2.1 Research Conceptual Framework

Information:

: Direct influence

: Indirect influence

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Normative Commitment

The research results of Badruddin (2019) and Solissa et al. (2022) in their research stated that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. According to Tumbelaka (2016:96), employees will never be separated from the culture of their organization. Because basically every organization is formed to achieve the goals it has set and the process of achieving those goals is what can ultimately form the interest, loyalty and commitment of each member of the organization so that they can behave in accordance with the guidelines of the cultural values of the organization. A conducive organizational culture can create compatibility for its members in carrying out work activities and will certainly have an impact

on the commitment of organizational members. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H1: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on normative commitment.

The Influence of Financial Compensation on Normative Commitment

There are several of them carried out by Dwiantono (2019); Basori (2020); Sari and Dewi (2020), who stated that financial compensation has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment. Furthermore, Monika et al., (2023:282) stated that providing incentives to employees can increase employee commitment in the long term. This is because providing incentives will encourage employee work motivation. The same thing is also explained in Ilyas's research (2022), financial compensation is related to the rights that employees will receive for the dedication and sacrifices given to their organization, so that if the company pays attention to the survival of its employees, then will stimulate the employee's commitment. On the other hand, if the compensation received by employees is unfair, unbalanced and uneven, it will have a negative impact on the organization. One of the impacts of employee dissatisfaction with the compensation received is a decrease in performance, high levels of absenteeism which leads to physical and psychological actions such as high levels of employee turnover. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H2: Financial compensation has a positive and significant effect on normative commitment.

The Effect of Interactional Organizational Justice on Commitment Normative

Research on interactional organizational justice has been conducted, including by: Nainaya et al., (2022); Yuliana and Suhana (2022), who stated that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Organizational commitment is formed by the emotional bonds formed by the company, such as the moral support felt by employees. One form of support can be organizational justice. Employees have their own assessment regarding fairness in the form of compensation, attention or treatment given by superiors. So when employees are treated fairly, their commitment will be stronger. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H3: Interactional organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

Research on organizational culture has been conducted by several researchers including: Jannah (2016); Joseph and Kibera (2019) where research results state that there is a significant positive influence between organizational culture and performance, meaning that the stronger the organizational culture, the better the performance of the organization's employees. According to Kusumawardani (2018), organizational culture is able to shape the behavior of each member of the organization in accordance with the values and norms that have been agreed and used as guidelines in organizing, so that every member of the organization's behavior that is in accordance with the values and norms of the organization is expected to realize the goals of the organization. Research conducted by Rahayu and Liana (2023) at Perumda Air Minum Tirta Bumi Serasih Semarang stated that the performance of Perumda Air Minum Tirta Bumi Serasih employees was very good, this was because the application of organizational culture by employees in the company was very high, this can be seen from The organizational culture implemented such as expressing the ability to work, high initiative and care for the work environment. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H4: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The Effect of Financial Compensation on Employee Performance

Research regarding the effect of compensation on employee performance has been conducted by several researchers, including: Arikxa et al., (2020); Yaqub et al., (2021) and Basori et al., (2020) state that financial compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. According to Monika et al., (2023), providing compensation can provide encouragement to organizational members to be able to work better and be more productive. On the other hand, providing compensation opens up opportunities for organizations to get quality employees. With compensation as a form of reward for services provided to the company, employees will be more enthusiastic about carrying out the work and responsibilities given by the company leadership. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H5: Financial compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The Effect of Interactional Organizational Justice on Performance Employee

Research by Sarianti et al., (2017), where the results of this research state that organizational justice, including procedural organizational justice, distributive organizational justice and interactional organizational justice, has a positive effect on performance. Research by Sarianti et al., (2017), is in line with research conducted by Reswandary et al., (2023), which states that interactional organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on employee performance in the Ponorogo Regency subdistrict office. Furthermore, Sarianti et al., (2017: 111), stated that organizational justice will influence the performance, emotions and behavior of human resources so that automatically individuals in the organization will be motivated to perform well as a form of remuneration for the justice they feel. in the organization. Manihuruk's research results (2023:124) also explain that one way to improve employee performance is to implement interactional justice to all employees, such as maintaining good communication between superiors and subordinates and providing equal treatment to all employees. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H6: Interactional organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The Effect of Normative Commitment on Employee Performance

Research on the influence of organizational commitment on employee performance was conducted by Nuryaningsih (2023), who stated that organizational commitment influences employee performance. This is because the organizational commitment that employees have is closely related to how employees show care and always prioritize their work within the organization, so that employees will voluntarily always give their best abilities and try to continue to develop their abilities so that they can help the organization achieve its goals. Nuryaningsih's research is in line with research by Simatupang et al., (2022) which states that organizational commitment has a positive effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment is a key to organizational

development. Because organizational commitment is related to the individual concept of employee life. The organization will benefit greatly if every employee has organizational commitment. Every employee who has high commitment will always try to contribute to good performance and create positive work achievements. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H7: Normative commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The Influence of Normative Commitment in Mediating Organizational Culture On Employee Performance

Research on the role of organizational commitment in mediating organizational culture on performance has been carried out by previous researchers, including the following: Kurniasari et al., (2018), where the results of the research show that organizational commitment can mediate the relationship between organizational culture and performance. This is because employees who have a perception of organizational culture are able to produce effective performance improvements if they have an attachment to their organization both affectively, normatively and continuously. This research is in line with research by Saputri and Muhsin (2018) which states that organizational culture implemented by the government cannot influence performance optimally without commitment from every member of the organization, this is because it appears suddenly but requires time and processes at each stage of its development so as to improve. For better performance, organizational commitment needs to be considered in several ways, including: involving all employees in every job. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H8: Normative commitment can mediate the relationship between organizational culture and performance.

The Effect of Normative Commitment in Mediating Financial Compensation On Employee Performance

Research that tested the influence of normative commitment in mediating the relationship between financial compensation and performance was previously conducted by Sung and Bahron (2018), where the research tested the mediating influence of 3 (three) types of organizational commitment, namely: affective commitment, normative commitment and continuous commitment. in mediating the effect of compensation on performance. The research results show that of the 3 (three) types of organizational commitment, only normative commitment can mediate the effect of financial compensation on performance. and there is an indirect influence between compensation on employee performance, this shows that providing compensation to employees does not directly have an impact on increasing their performance if the employee does not have a commitment to improving their performance in the organization. Meanwhile, according to Oktaviani and Pramusinto (2019: 828), normative commitment itself can influence employees because of the effect of psychological contracts in the form of personal contracts such as work agreement terms which reflect workers' beliefs about what they should give in return for what the organization has provided so far. Based on the results of several previous studies above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H9: Normative commitment can mediate the relationship between financial compensation and performance.

The Effect of Normative Commitment in Mediating Organizational Justice Interaction on Employee Performance

Research on the influence of organizational justice on performance as mediated by organizational commitment was previously carried out by Kuncoro (2021), where the research results stated that organizational commitment can mediate the influence of interactional organizational justice on employee performance. Organizational justice is one of the important things in motivating employees in the work environment, this is because organizational justice can be used as a tool in increasing the effectiveness of organizational functions and job satisfaction which has an impact on increasing the performance of each individual in the organization. Employees in organizations tend to compare the contributions they have made to the organization with what they obtain from their organization (Kuncoro, 2021). Based on the results of previous research above, alternative hypotheses that can be formulated are: H10: Normative commitment can mediate the relationship between financial compensation and performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

Population is an area that is generally determined by researchers as the unit of analysis to be studied and concluded. The population consists of objects/subjects that have quantities and characteristics. Population is not only people, but can also be inanimate objects and other natural objects. In a study, population does not only refer to the number of objects or subjects to be studied, but rather to the characteristics or traits possessed by these subjects and objects (Sugiyono, 2019: 126). The population in this study was all employees of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember, namely 240 people (Data Source: Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember Personnel Data for September 2022).

The sample is part of the population to be studied. Using samples in research will make it easier for researchers to collect data when compared to collecting data from the total population. Apart from that, the use of samples in research is much more effective and efficient or saves costs, energy, time and equipment. In determining the number of samples to be used in research, there is a method called a sampling technique. The purpose of the sampling technique is so that researchers can obtain a representative sample of the total population (Alma, 2018: 56). The sampling technique used in this research is simple random sampling technique. According to Alma (2018:65), in a research population, there are those whose population numbers are unknown and there are also those whose population numbers are known. If the population size is known, the sample calculation can use the Isaac and Michel formula. The Isaac and Michael formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Information:

- n : Number of samples required
- N : Number of Population
- e : Sample error rate (sampling error of 5%)

It is known that the total population used in this research was 240 employees. Based on Isaac and Michael's formula, the sample that will be used in this research is:

$$n = \frac{240}{1 + 240(0,05)^2} = 150 \text{ Employee}$$

Data Sources and Data Collection Methods

The data sources used in this research are primary and secondary data.

1) Primary Data

Primary data is data obtained by researchers directly (Sugiyono, 2019:296). In this case, primary data was obtained by researchers through distributing questionnaires to employees of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember.

2) Secondary Data

Secondary data is data obtained by researchers through other parties or indirectly (Sugiyono, 2019:296). In this case, the secondary data obtained by researchers is data on the number of employees of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember, journals and scientific articles used as research support.

The data collection method is a method used by researchers to obtain valid and reliable data. There are several data collection methods such as distributing questionnaires, observation, interviews, observations, tests and documentation. It is not necessary to use all of these methods in carrying out research, because every data collection method in research must include data. Therefore, to be more efficient, if one of these techniques is deemed sufficient, then other techniques should not be used (Alma, 2018:98). The data collection method used in this research is:

1. Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a method of collecting data by giving a set of questions to respondents (Sugiyono, 2019:199). The statement given to the respondent is an indicator of the variable to be studied. In this case, the indicators that will later be used as questions to respondents are indicators of the variables organizational culture, work involvement, compensation, organizational commitment and employee performance.

2. Documentation

Documentation is data obtained directly from the research site, including photos and documentation when carrying out research activities.

Research variable

Research variables are attributes in various forms that have been determined by researchers to be studied and concluded. In research, variables are one of the attributes used in quantitative research. Each variable must have variation as a condition for it to be researched. To be able to vary, research must be based on a group of varied data sources or objects (Sugiyono, 2019:67).

Independent Variable

Independent variables or commonly called independent variables, stimulus variables, predictors, antecedents. The independent variable is a variable that can influence the dependent variable or dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2019:69). In this research there are three independent variables that will be studied. The three independent variables are: Organizational Culture, Financial Compensation and Interactional Organizational Justice.

Intervening Variables

Intervening variables are usually called intermediate variables, so that the location of the intervening variable is between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Theoretically, intervening variables influence the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable into a relationship that is indirect or cannot be measured directly. In research, independent variables cannot always influence the dependent variable directly, therefore the function of intervening variables in research is as an intermediary between the independent variable and the dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2019:70). The intervening variable used in this research is normative commitment.

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable is usually referred to as the dependent variable or output or consequence variable. The dependent variable is a variable that is influenced by the independent variable (Sugiyono, 2019:69). The dependent variable (Y) in this research is the performance of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember employees.

Research Instrument

Research instruments in research are used as a tool to collect data and measure the value of each research variable. Research instruments must have accurate measuring tools in order to produce conclusions from the data collected, therefore each variable must have a scale. The types of scales that are often used in administrative, educational and social research are the Linkert Scale, Guttman Scale, Rating Scale and Semantic Deferential (Sugiyono, 2019: 156). The scale used in this research is the Linkert scale.

The Likert scale is often used to measure the attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person or group of people towards a social phenomenon. The Linkert scale measurements for each research variable will describe the indicators and then arrange them into instruments which can be in the form of questions or statements (Sugiyono, 2019: 146). The Likert scale levels are arranged from the most positive to the most negative. The Linkert scale research instrument can be made in the form of a checklist or multiple choice. In this research, the Linkert scale form used is a checklist, where each respondent will put a check mark (√) on each answer they choose in the column provided. And the levels of answer criteria in this research instrument are as follows:

Table 2.1 Criteria and levels of respondents' answers

Answers	Score
Strongly agree	5
Agree	4
Quite agree	3
Disagree	2
Strongly disagree	1

Source: Sugiyono (2019)

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

The purpose of the data analysis method is one of the steps in research to draw conclusions and test the hypothesis to be tested. This research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). According to Hamid and Anwar (2019:1), SEM analysis in empirical research, especially in the business sector, is often used by researchers to test several research models that are complex or consist of many variables and indicators. Furthermore, Hamid and Anwar (2019:2), SEM has 2 types, namely: variance-based SEM and covariance-based SEM. Covariance-based SEM demands a strong theoretical basis, meets various parametric assumptions and meets the GOF (Goodness of Fit) test. Therefore, covariance-based SEM is more suitable for use in testing a theory, while variance-based SEM or VB-SEM is used to test predictive relationships between constructs by seeing whether there is a relationship or influence between the constructs. This research uses variance-based SEM with the help of the SmartPLS 3.0 statistical tool.

According to Muliawati (2018:35), PLS is an analytical tool that allows researchers to obtain latent variable values for prediction purposes. PLS has the advantage of being able to estimate large and complex models with hundreds of latent variables and thousands of indicators. Muliawati (2018:36) further stated that if a study is in a situation of high complexity and has a sample size of less than 200, then SEM analysis using PLS is more appropriate to apply. According to Duryadi (2021:61), in SEM testing there are 2 model evaluations, namely: outer model evaluation and inner model evaluation.

Outer Model Evaluation

Outer Analysis or (Measurement Model) was carried out to determine the validity and reliability of the data collected (Duryadi, 2021:61). Meanwhile, according to Hamid and Anwar (2019:41), outer model evaluation testing is often also called construct validity testing. Testing of this outer model consists of convergent validity testing and discriminant validity testing.

1) Convergent Validity, convergent validity testing is a test to test the magnitude of the correlation between indicators and latent variables. (Junianto and Sabtohadhi, 2020). An indicator is said to be acceptable and able to explain the latent variable if it has a good validity value. According to Duryadi (2021:62), an indicator is said to have good validity if the outer loading factor has a value of >0.7 for confirmatory research and >0.6 for explanatory research. Furthermore, according to Duryadi (2021), an indicator is said to meet the requirements of the convergent validity test if the loading factor value is >0.5 . The stage for conducting a convergent validity test using SmartPLS software is to select the project data to be processed then select the calculate menu and select the PLS Algorithm sheet. The convergent validity test in the SmartPLS application can be seen in the outer loading factor value in the final result menu (Hamid and Anwar, 2019:42).

2) Discriminant validity test, discriminant validity testing aims to measure the correlation between several different constructs. The discriminant validity test was carried out by looking at the square root value of AVE (Average Variance Extracted). Each indicator is said to be able to explain the variable compared to other latent variables if the square root of AVE $>$ the correlation between other constructs (Duryadi, 2021:62). The stage for discriminant validity testing using SmartPLS software is to select the project data to be tested, then select the calculate menu after the PLS Algorithm sheet appears, select discriminant validity in the quality criteria menu.

3) Reliability test, this test is carried out to determine the degree of consistency of the data collection instrument. It is said to be reliable if there are other researchers who carry out research using the same method, then the resulting data will also be the same (Sugiyono, 2019: 362). The reliability test was carried out by looking at the Cronbach alpha value and composite reliability value. The reliability value is declared good if the Cronbach alpha value and composite reliability value are >0.7 (Hamid and Anwar, 2019:42). The steps for testing convergent validity in SmartPLS software are to select the project data to be processed then select the calculate menu and select PLS Algorithm. On the quality criteria menu, select the construct reliability and validity menu, the Cronbach alpha value can be seen in the left column of the table.

4) Statistical Collinearity Test (VIF), a collinearity test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables are not correlated with other independent variables in one model. Collinearity statistics testing is carried out by looking at the VIF value, if the VIF value is ≤ 5.0 then there are no symptoms of multicollinearity in each independent variable (Siswantoro et al., 2023). The stage for testing collinearity statistics in SmartPLS software is to select the project data to be analyzed then select the calculate menu, then select PLS Algorithm, after the PLS Algorithm sheet appears then select collinearity statistics (VIF) in the quality criteria menu.

Inner Model Testing (Structural Model Evaluation)

Inner Model testing includes testing the R-Square value and path coefficient (Path Coefficient) which consists of direct and indirect effects:

1) R-Square Test, the R-Square test is used to measure the level of variation in changes in the independent variable towards the dependent variable. (Hamid and Anwar, 2019:43), The structural model evaluation criteria for the R-Square test are as follows: R-Square value 0.19, the influence of exogenous on endogenous is weak; 0.33 moderate exogenous to endogenous

influence; 0.67 strong exogenous influence on endogenous. The R-Square test stage in the Smart-PLS application is: by selecting the project data to be processed then selecting the calculate menu and selecting PLS Algorithm. On the quality criteria menu, select the R-Square menu. The R-Square value can be seen in the R Square table column on the left.

2) Path Coefficient, testing the path coefficient is testing the research hypothesis. This test was carried out to determine the effect of a two-tailed test or two-way influence (positive and negative). To find out the two-way effect, it can be seen through the original value of the sample. If the sample original value shows a positive value, it indicates that there is a one-way variable relationship, whereas if the sample original value is negative, it indicates an inverse variable relationship. Apart from that, the path coefficient is also used to determine the p-value if the p-value < 0.05 then the exogenous variable has a significant influence on the endogenous variable (Duryadi, 2021:63). The steps for carrying out the path coefficient test with the SmartPLS application can be done by selecting the project data to be processed, then selecting the calculate menu then selecting the bootstrapping menu after the bootstrapping sheet appears, selecting path coefficients in the final results menu. The original sample value is in the original sample table column on the left, while the p-value is in the p-value table column on the right.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

1) Convergent Validity Test

The condition for testing convergent validity is if the outer loading value is > 0.5 (Duryadi, 2021:63). The following are the results of convergent validity testing for each latent variable indicator in this study:

Table 3.1 Outer Loading Value

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Organizational culture (X ₁)	X _{1.1}	0,699
	X _{1.2}	0,828
	X _{1.3}	0,802
	X _{1.4}	0,766
	X _{1.5}	0,788
Financial Compensation (X ₂)	X _{2.1}	0,890
	X _{2.2}	0,929
	X _{2.3}	0,767
Interactional Organizational Justice (X ₃)	X _{3.1}	0,914
	X _{3.2}	0,931
Normative Commitment (Z)	Z _{1.1}	0,730
	Z _{1.2}	0,857
	Z _{1.3}	0,844
	Z _{1.4}	0,811
Employee performance (Y)	Y _{1.1}	0,767
	Y _{1.2}	0,809
	Y _{1.3}	0,867
	Y _{1.4}	0,818
	Y _{1.5}	0,805

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

Based on Table 3.1 It is known that the value of each indicator of the variables organizational culture, financial compensation, interactional organizational justice, normative commitment and employee performance has an outer loading value of > 0.5 so that all indicators are declared valid and meet the requirements for convergent validity testing.

2) Discriminant Validity Test

The discriminant validity test was carried out by looking at the square root value of AVE (Average Variance Extracted). The square root value of AVE is said to have good validity when the following is the square root value of AVE $>$ the correlation between other latent constructs (Junianto and Sabtohadhi, 2020). The results of discriminant validity testing can be seen in table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Square Root Value

	Organizational culture	Interactional Organizational Justice	Employee performance	Normative Commitment	Financial Compensation
Organizational culture	0,778				
Interactional Organizational Justice	0,454	0,922			
Employee performance	0,432	0,411	0,814		
Normative Commitment	0,230	0,405	0,634	0,812	

Financial Compensation	0,173	0,393	0,208	0,357	0,865
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Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

In the table above, it is known that the AVE root value obtained by each indicator is greater than the AVE root value of each latent variable below it so that the discriminant validity in this study is declared valid and meets the requirements of the discriminant validity test.

3) Reliability Test

The reliability test in this research was carried out using the Cronbach's alpha method and the composite reliability method. If the Cronbach's alpha value and composite reliability value are >0.7 then it is declared reliable or meets the requirements of the reliability test. The results of the reliability test can be seen in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3 Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Organizational culture	0,839	0,884	Reliable
Financial Compensation	0,833	0,899	Reliable
Interactional	0,825	0,919	Reliable
Organizational Justice	0,827	0,886	Reliable
Normative Commitment	0,827	0,886	Reliable
Employee performance	0,872	0,907	Reliable

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

Based on the reliability test results, it is known that the Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values are >0.7 , so they are declared reliable and meet the requirements for reliability testing. Thus, it can be concluded that the variable measuring instruments in this study are reliable.

4) Statistical Collinearity Test (VIF)

The collinearity test was carried out to test whether in this study there was a correlation between the independent variables. The statistical collinearity test is carried out by looking at the value of the VIF. If the VIF value is <5 , it is stated that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables in the study. The results of the Collinearity Statistics (VIF) test can be seen in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4 Collinearity Statistics (VIF) Test Results

Variabel	VIF	VIF
Organizational culture (X_1)	1,265	1,260
Financial Compensation (X_2)	1,252	1,182
Interactional Organizational Justice (X_3)	1,549	1,445
Normative Commitment (Z)	1,271	

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

Based on the collinearity statistics (VIF) test, it can be seen that the VIF value for each variable is <5 , so it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables in this study.

Inner Model Testing

1) R-Square Testing

The R-Square test is carried out to see the suitability between latent variables in a model (Junianto and Sabtohadhi, 2020), if the R-square value is 0.67, it means the influence of the endogenous variable on the exogenous variable is strong, if the R-Square value is 0.19, it means the influence Endogenous variables on exogenous variables are weak and if the R-square value is 0.33, it means that the influence of endogenous variables on exogenous variables is moderate. The R-square test results can be seen in table 3.5

Table 3.5 R-Square Value

Variable	R-square value	Information
Normative Commitment	0,213	Weak
Employee performance	0,495	Currently

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

Based on the results of the R-square test in Table 3.5, it is known that the R-square value for the normative commitment variable is 0.213, which can be interpreted as meaning that the influence of organizational culture, financial compensation and interactional organizational justice variables on normative commitment is 21.3% while the remaining 78.7 % influenced by other variables outside this research. The R-square value of the employee performance variable is 0.495, which means that 49.5% of the employee performance variable is influenced by organizational culture, interactional organizational justice, while the remaining 50.5% is influenced by other variables outside the research.

2) Path Coefficient

Path coefficient testing is hypothesis testing in this research. Whether a hypothesis is accepted or not can be determined through testing the path coefficient. There are 2 (two) path coefficient tests, namely direct influence and indirect influence. Hypothesis testing in this research can be accepted if the resulting P-values are <0.05 . Meanwhile, to find out the direction of the relationship between variables is determined through the original sample value. The results of testing the path coefficient in the research can be seen in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6 Path Coefficient Values of Direct Influence Between Variables

Variable	Original Sample	P-value	Results
$X_1 - Z$	0,060	0,525	Positive, not significant
$X_1 - Y$	0,276	0,000	Positive, significant
$X_2 - Z$	0,234	0,003	Positive, significant
$X_2 - Y$	-0,075	0,250	Negative, insignificant
$X_3 - Z$	0,286	0,001	Positive, significant
$X_3 - Y$	0,088	0,273	Positive, not significant
$Z - Y$	0,561	0,000	Positive, significant

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

Based on testing the direct influence from Table 3.6 above, it can be seen that:

- The original sample value of Organizational Culture (X_1) on Normative Commitment (Z) is $\beta = 0.060$ which indicates a positive or unidirectional direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.525 > 0.05$ or show insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is no significant influence between organizational culture and normative commitment. Thus the first hypothesis is rejected.
- The original sample value of Financial Compensation (X_2) to Normative Commitment (Z) is $\beta = 0.234$ which shows a positive or unidirectional direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.003 < 0.05$ or show significant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between financial compensation and normative commitment. Thus the second hypothesis is accepted.
- The original sample value of Interactional Organizational Justice (X_3) on Normative Commitment (Z) is $\beta = 0.286$ which shows a positive or unidirectional direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.001 < 0.05$ or show significant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between interactional organizational justice and normative commitment. Thus the third hypothesis is accepted.
- The original sample value of Organizational Culture (X_1) on Employee Performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.276$ which shows a positive or unidirectional direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.000 < 0.05$ or show significant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between organizational culture on employee performance. Thus the fourth hypothesis is accepted.
- The original sample value of Financial Compensation (X_2) on Employee Performance (Y) is $\beta = (-0.075)$ which shows a negative or opposite direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.250 > 0.05$ or show insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is no significant influence between financial compensation and employee performance. Thus the fifth hypothesis is rejected.
- The original sample value of Interactional Organizational Justice (X_3) on Employee Performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.088$ which shows a positive or unidirectional direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.273 > 0.05$ or show insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is no significant influence between interactional organizational justice on employee performance. Thus the sixth hypothesis is rejected.
- The original sample value of Normative Commitment (Z) on Employee Performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.561$ which shows a positive or unidirectional direction. Meanwhile, the p-values are $0.000 < 0.05$ or show insignificant results. Based on the original sample calculation values and p-values, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between normative commitment on employee performance. Thus the seventh hypothesis is accepted.

To determine the role of the normative commitment variable as a mediating variable between organizational culture, financial compensation and interactional organizational justice on employee performance, it can be seen in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7 Indirect Influence Path Coefficient Values

Variable	P-Values	Information
$X_1 \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$	0,531	Not significant
$X_2 \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$	0,004	Significant
$X_3 \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$	0,006	Significant

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023.

Based on the indirect influence path coefficient values in Table 3.7, it can be seen that:

- The indirect influence of Normative Commitment (Z) on the influence of Organizational Culture (X_1) and Employee Performance (Y) has an insignificant value. This can be proven by the resulting P-values being greater than 0.05. This means that normative commitment cannot mediate the relationship between organizational culture and employee performance. Thus the eighth hypothesis is rejected.
- The indirect influence of Normative Commitment (Z) on the influence of Financial Compensation (X_2) and Employee Performance (Y) has a significant value. This can be proven by the resulting P-values being smaller than 0.05. This means that normative commitment can mediate the relationship between financial compensation and employee performance. Thus the ninth hypothesis is accepted.
- The indirect influence of Normative Commitment (Z) on the influence of Interactional Organizational Justice (X_3) and Employee Performance (Y) has a significant value. This can be proven by the resulting P-values being smaller than 0.05. This means that normative commitment can mediate the relationship between interactional organizational justice and employee performance. Thus the tenth hypothesis is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Normative Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is no significant influence between organizational culture and normative commitment. This can be proven by the resulting P-values of 0.525 or > 0.05 . Organizational culture is the values embedded in an organization that are believed to be used as guidelines for organizational members to behave in accordance with the wishes of the organization. Theoretically and in previous research, organizational culture is able to build employee organizational commitment. However, this is different from the results of this research, where organizational culture does not have a significant effect on employee normative commitment. This shows that basically the normative commitment that every employee of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember has is formed without going through organizational culture.

This research is in line with research conducted by Utomo (2022), that organizational culture has a direct influence on performance but does not directly influence the organizational commitment of PDAM Wonogiri Regency employees. The results of this research are also supported by the research results of Colquitt et al., (2015), which states that there are 2 (two) factors in building employee commitment, namely: direct factors and indirect factors. Factors that directly influence employee commitment are job satisfaction, motivation, stress, organizational justice, ethics, trust, learning and decision making, while factors that indirectly influence organizational culture include organizational culture, organizational structure, leadership, leadership style, team characteristics and process.

The Influence of Financial Compensation on Normative Commitments

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a positive and significant influence between financial compensation and employee normative commitment. The results of data analysis show that the p-values are 0.006 or < 0.05 and the path coefficient value is 0.234. This means that if the compensation given to employees in financial form includes: providing salaries in accordance with workload, providing bonuses and good religious allowances, the employee's normative commitment will increase.

This research supports Dwiantono's research (2019); Basori (2020); Sari and Dewi (2020) and Monika et. Al., (2022), which states that financial compensation has a positive effect on employee organizational commitment. Providing financial compensation is related to the rights that employees will receive for the service and sacrifices given to their organization. If the company pays attention to the survival of its employees, a normative commitment will arise within the employee. This normative commitment is demonstrated through the behavior of employees who always comply with applicable rules and norms, a sense of responsibility for the company's progress arises, and strive to provide the best performance as a form of remuneration for what the company has provided so far. This research supports research by Sari and Dewi (2020) which states that compensation has a significant effect on employee organizational commitment.

The Influence of Interactional Organizational Justice on Normative Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a positive and significant influence between interpersonal organizational justice and employee normative commitment. The results of data analysis show a P-value of 0.001 or < 0.05 and the path coefficient value shows a positive direction, namely 0.286. This means that the better the interactional organizational justice, the better the normative commitment possessed by employees. This research is in line with research by Nainaya et al., (2022); Yuliani and Suhana (2022), who stated that organizational justice has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

The relationship between superiors and subordinates has an important influence in building employee organizational commitment. Interactional organizational justice is implemented through the relationship between superiors and subordinates in an organization, leaders who treat their subordinates well and are able to provide logical work instructions can build good emotional bonds between employees and the company, with moral support from superiors to subordinates it is proven to be able to foster positive perceptions of employees towards their organization.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a positive and significant influence between the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. The results of data analysis from hypothesis testing show a P-value of 0.000 or < 0.05 and the path coefficient value shows a positive direction, namely 0.276. This means that the better the organizational culture at Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember, the better employee performance will be. The results of this research support previous research conducted by Jannah (2016); Joseph and Kibera (2019) where research results also show that there is a significant positive influence between organizational culture and performance.

Organizational culture is able to shape the behavior of each member of the organization in accordance with agreed values and norms and is used as a guideline in organizing, every behavior of organizational members that is in accordance with organizational values and norms certainly has a positive impact on the organization, with a competitive organizational culture it will encourage employees to continue improve its performance to be even better.

The Effect of Financial Compensation on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is no significant influence between financial compensation and employee performance. This can be proven by the resulting P-values of 0.241 or > 0.05 . In this research, financial compensation has no direct effect on performance. This research is in line with research by Rizal et al., (2014) where financial compensation is able to increase employee organizational commitment, but does not have a significant effect on employee performance and research by Kurniawan et al., (2022) which states that compensation has no effect on employee performance. According to Shanty and Mayangsari (2017), there is a goal setting theory that is able to explain why financial compensation has no influence on performance, employees who know their goals at work always provide their best performance without paying attention to the

compensation they will receive. Apart from that, compensation is closely related to meeting employee needs. If you pay attention to Maslow's theory, financial compensation does not affect employee performance because employee basic needs which include physiological needs and security needs have been met, so employees are more focused on fulfilling their psychological needs which include relationships between fellow employees, well-established trust in superiors and the need for self-fulfillment which includes the need for appreciation and recognition.

The Effect of Interactional Organizational Justice on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is no significant influence between interactional organizational justice on employee performance. This can be proven by the resulting P-values of 0.273 or > 0.05 . The results of this research are different from the results of research conducted by Sarianti et al., (2017); Reswandary et al., (2023) and Manihuruk (2023), where the results of this research state that organizational justice has a positive effect on employee performance. In this research, interactional organizational justice does not have a direct effect on performance without the normative commitment of employees. Interactional organizational justice within the Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember organization has been going well. However, interpersonal organizational justice does not have a significant influence on the performance of Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember employees. This proves that interactional organizational justice is not an influential factor in improving employee performance, no matter how good the treatment and communication between superiors and subordinates, not directly able to improve employee performance, if the employee does not have commitment and awareness in carrying out the tasks that have become his responsibility. Interactional organizational justice only has a direct effect on employee normative commitment. Fair treatment and moral support from superiors towards subordinates can create a conducive work situation for employees. If this conducive situation lasts in the long term then over time there will be compatibility and interest among employees towards the organization and in the next stage commitment will arise from the employees.

The Effect of Normative Commitment on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a positive and significant influence between normative commitment on employee performance. This can be proven by the resulting P-values of 0.00 or < 0.05 and the path coefficient value which shows a positive direction, namely 0.561. This means that the better the employee's commitment, the better the resulting performance. The results of this research are in line with research by Nuryaningsih (2023) and Simatupang (2022), which states that organizational commitment influences employee performance.

The organizational commitment that employees have is closely related to how employees show they care about their organization, employees who have high commitment always prioritize their work affairs within the organization over other matters and voluntarily want to give their best abilities and the desire to continue to improve their abilities so that they can help the organization in achieve its goal. Employees who have normative commitment in the organization always obey the rules and norms that apply in their organization so that the behavior and habits shown in the organization are always positive.

The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Through Normative Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is no significant role of employee commitment as a mediator of the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. The results of data analysis show that the P-values are 0.531 or > 0.05 . The results of this research are different from research conducted by Kurniasari et al., (2018); Saputri and Muhsin (2018), who stated that organizational commitment is able to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. The results of this research are in line with research from Budiono (2016), where the research results state that the influence of organizational culture on performance through organizational commitment is smaller than the direct influence of organizational culture on employee performance.

The organizational culture that exists within the Perumdam Tirta Pandalungan Jember environment is an important determinant of employee performance. The existence of a strong and competitive organizational culture has been proven to be able to influence employee performance, because the existence of a strong organizational culture can indirectly bind employees to continue to be productive and behave positively.

The Effect of Financial Compensation on Employee Performance Through Normative Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a significant role of employee normative commitment as a mediator of the influence of financial compensation on employee performance. The results of data analysis show that the P-values are 0.004 or < 0.05 . The results of this research are in line with research by Sung and Bahron (2018) which states that providing compensation to employees does not directly have an impact on increasing their performance if the employee does not have a commitment to improving their performance in the organization.

Providing compensation in good financial form and in accordance with the employee's workload is able to build normative commitment in employees, this is because employees have the perception that the company has paid attention to their welfare for their service to the company, so that a normative commitment arises within these employees to help the organization achieve the goals that have been set, they also assume that if the continuity of the company's business processes is maintained then their welfare will also be guaranteed. Employees with normative commitment also always want to contribute to the company's progress as a form of gratitude for what the organization has provided.

The Influence of Interactional Organizational Justice on Employee Performance Through Normative Commitment

The results of hypothesis testing show that normative commitment can significantly mediate the influence of interactional organizational justice on employee performance. The results of data analysis show P-values of 0.006 or < 0.05 . The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Kuncoro (2021), where the results of this research also show the role of organizational commitment in the relationship between interpersonal organizational justice and employee performance.

Improving employee performance is closely related to building commitment from the employees themselves. The results of this research indicate that interactional organizational justice has a significant influence in increasing employee normative

commitment. Employees who feel they have received justice in the workplace will continue to maintain their jobs and strive to provide their best performance so that their organization can achieve its stated goals.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion of data analysis, the following conclusions can be obtained:

1. Organizational culture has no significant effect on normative commitment. The results of this research indicate that the first hypothesis (H1) is rejected.
2. Financial compensation has a significant effect on normative commitment. The results of this research indicate that the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.
3. Interactional organizational justice has a significant effect on normative commitment. The results of this research indicate that the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted.
4. Organizational culture has a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research show that the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted.
5. Financial compensation does not have a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the fifth hypothesis (H5) is rejected.
6. Interactional organizational justice has no significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the sixth hypothesis (H6) is rejected.
7. Normative commitment has a significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the seventh hypothesis (H7) is accepted.
8. Normative commitment has no significant effect in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the eighth hypothesis (H8) is rejected.
9. Normative commitment has a significant effect in mediating the effect of financial compensation on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the ninth hypothesis (H9) is accepted.
10. Normative commitment has a significant effect in mediating the influence of interactional organizational justice on employee performance. The results of this research indicate that the tenth research hypothesis (H10) is accepted.

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